
Slice of Understanding: Art Elements Pie Chart

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Summary— The paper, titled "Slice of Understanding: Art Elements Pie Chart," detailed an innovative educational tool developed by Arnel Jeff S. Tulabing at F. Bangoy National High School. Implemented in August 2023, this tool aimed to address students' challenges in analyzing art elements due to abstract concepts and subjective interpretations. The "Art Elements Pie Chart" provided a visually engaging and interactive method for students to understand and analyze key art components, including line, shape, form, color, texture, and space. By breaking down these complex elements into digestible segments, the chart facilitated a clearer comprehension and enhanced analytical skills. The innovation aligned with the Department of Education's goals of promoting holistic and inclusive education, offering practical and accessible learning aids that fostered critical thinking and artistic appreciation. The implementation process involved integrating the pie chart into lesson plans, conducting formative assessments, and receiving feedback to refine its effectiveness continually. The project demonstrated a successful synthesis of technology, methodology, and pedagogical principles, significantly improving students' understanding and engagement with art elements.

Keywords— Art, Pie Chart, Elements, Segments, Slice of understanding

I. OVERVIEW

Students struggle with analyzing art elements due to abstract concepts like symbolism and abstraction, alongside interpreting the subjective nature of artistic expression within historical and cultural contexts. Addison et.al (2018) mentioned that students encounter difficulties while trying to understand art elements like form, color, composition, and symbolism and suggests ways to improve their comprehension in learning environments. It clarifies the difficulties involved in evaluating artistic aspects and offers useful strategies for enhancing students' understanding and interpretation of art. The "Art Elements Pie Chart" provides a visually engaging tool for students to comprehend and analyze art elements more effectively. By facilitating clearer understanding and interpretation of art, it fosters enriched learning experiences, empowers educators, and cultivates a more art-literate community. Based on the facts it clearly shows that the students are having a hard time analyzing the elements of art as observed in the result of the least learned competencies. Certainly, as an art educator, I face challenges in explaining and teaching the analysis of art elements and characteristics while considering additional factors. The Art Elements Pie Chart offers visual representation, breaking down complex art elements into digestible segments, aiding students in understanding abstract concepts like line, shape, texture, form,

space, color, and value. Its insightful design simplifies the analysis process, enabling students to grasp the relationships between various elements, thereby enhancing their comprehension and analytical skills in art.

In keeping with the vision, mission, and objectives of the Department of Education, the "Art Elements Pie Chart" uses practical and visual learning aids to improve students' understanding of art elements. It contributes to the Department's goal of promoting holistic education by giving students a structured and accessible means for exploring artistic elements. In addition, the chart contributes to students' overall academic development and progress by making it easier for students to understand art elements, which supports the Department's purpose of encouraging excellence in education. Also, the Art Elements Pie Chart embodies the school's division office's commitment to inclusive and creative art education, providing an accessible tool for diverse learners. By fostering critical thinking and artistic expression, it advances the school's division office's goals of holistic student development and academic excellence in the arts. Furthermore, it aligns with the MATATAG curriculum of the Department of Education by promoting comprehensive and inclusive education in the arts. It supports the Department of Education's vision of providing structured and accessible learning tools that aid students in exploring artistic elements, thus fostering their overall academic development and progress. Moreover, the chart embodies the values of inclusive and creative art education advocated by the Department of Education's MATATAG curriculum, serving as a practical tool for diverse learners to enhance critical thinking and artistic expression.

II. INNOVATION DESCRIPTION

The Art Elements Pie Chart is a comprehensive visual tool designed to aid students in understanding and analyzing various elements of art. Its circular diagram features distinct sections for elements like form, color, line, shape, texture, and space, enabling easy identification and differentiation. The first pie is presented by lines which are marks move within space, conveying stroke movement, direction, and intention, allowing viewers to visualize orientation (authentic, implicit, vertical, horizontal, diagonal and outline lines). The second pie is presented by shape which is encased by lines to signify its height and width structure (Geometrical, One-dimensional, and Straight-lined). The third pie is presented by form which is a three-dimensional object with volume of height, width, and depth (volume, depth, and mass). The fourth pie is presented by color which is an element consisting of hues, of which there are three properties: hue, chroma or intensity, and value (light, neutral and dark). The fifth pie is presented by texture and is used to describe the surface quality of the work, referencing the types of lines the artist created (tactile (real) and strictly visual (implied)). And the last pie is presented by space which refers to the perspective (distance between and around) and proportion (size) between shapes and objects and how their relationship with the foreground or background is perceived (positive, negative, and open and closed space).

With clear labels and definitions accompanying each segment, students gain a basic understanding of the characteristics and significance of each element. Interactive features may enhance learning by providing supplementary resources and examples, while accompanying educational materials offer guidance on classroom integration. Portable and versatile, the chart is suitable for diverse educational settings and grade levels, making it an indispensable resource for educators and students alike in exploring and comprehending the fundamental principles of visual arts.

The Art Elements Pie Chart represents a synthesis of technology, methodology, and principles aimed at enhancing students' comprehension and analysis of art elements. Leveraging visual design principles, interactive technology, pedagogical methodologies, and accessibility features, the chart ensures clarity, engagement, and inclusivity in the learning process. By integrating various art theories, contexts, and cultural perspectives, it fosters critical thinking and appreciation for artistic diversity. Ultimately, the chart serves as a dynamic and comprehensive tool that empowers students to explore, understand, and interpret art elements with depth and insight.

To demonstrate the process, the teacher uses art element pie charts to illustrate the creative process. Each slice represents a key aspect of art, aiding students in understanding artwork, and when the slice will be pulled over there will be an indicator that aids the students to better understand the artwork and easily analyze the elements of art. This visual aid enhances comprehension and appreciation for various artistic expressions presented in class.

III. INNOVATION STATEMENT

The utilization of the Art Elements Pie Chart in educational settings encompasses several overarching goals and objectives. Primarily, it serves to facilitate students' comprehension of the fundamental elements of art, including color, form, line, shape, texture, and space, by offering a visual aid. Through the breakdown of artworks into individual elements represented by each slice of the chart, students are empowered to analyze and interpret artistic compositions effectively, recognizing the nuanced contributions of different elements to the overall aesthetic. This process not only deepens their appreciation for artworks but also fosters critical discussion and constructive critique, encouraging students to articulate their insights regarding the application of various art elements. Moreover, the pie chart acts as a catalyst for creativity, inspiring students to experiment and innovate within their own artistic endeavors, while also accommodating diverse learning styles, particularly benefiting visual learners by providing a tangible representation of abstract artistic concepts.

IV. IMPLEMENTATION PROCEDURE

a. Process Flow Framework

The process flow for implementing the Art Elements Pie Chart involves several pivotal stages. Beginning with the identification of learning objectives, teachers determine the essential concepts and skills pertaining to the elements of art. Subsequently, they select and develop clear explanations for the art elements to be included, ensuring alignment with curriculum goals. Designing an aesthetically pleasing layout and integrating the chart into instructional materials follow suit, offering students opportunities for engagement and exploration. Concurrently, ongoing assessment and feedback mechanisms gauge student comprehension and inform instructional adjustments. Reflection on the chart's efficacy prompts revisions to enhance its role as a valuable tool for teaching and learning about art elements. Through these concerted efforts, educators facilitate meaningful exploration and understanding of the elements of art within the classroom setting.

Alignment with learning objectives is necessary for the Art Elements Pie Chart innovation to work well and ensure that learning objectives are relevant and effectively met. By creating content with careful consideration and incorporating it smoothly into teaching resources, teachers convey art concepts in a way that makes sense and encourages students to explore and participate. Teachers can improve student learning experiences and encourage meaningful comprehension of art elements, enhancing the quality of art education in the classroom, with the support of continual assessment, reflection, and revision processes in addition to teacher training.

Teachers who use the Art Elements Pie Chart can improve student engagement and improve curriculum development by utilizing digital platforms and multimedia tools to help students get a deeper grasp of art elements. Frequent teacher development workshops and collaborative learning communities support the continuous enhancement of instructional approaches, guaranteeing that the chart's efficacy as a teaching tool is enhanced over time.

Fig. 1: Steps In Slice of Understanding

Fig. 2: Process Flow

b. Project Management

In implementing the Art Elements Pie Chart involved ensuring equitable access for all students in the class to the required materials, enabling universal utilization. The accessibility of the materials used in constructing the chart was prioritized to enhance its ease of use and seamless integration into instructional practices. The teacher guides discussions, presents examples, and offers support to help students understand and apply the concepts and techniques embedded in the art element pie chart. As recipients of this inno-

vative teaching tool, students absorb knowledge and skills from the teacher's instruction to improve their proficiency and comprehension in analyzing the elements of art in a particular artwork. Effective implementation of the innovation hinges on essential project management tactics such as defining explicit objectives, precise scheduling, and resource distribution, coupled with consistent progress assessments and evaluations. These strategies streamline operations, address potential risks, and ensure alignment with desired results. Specifically, for the Art Elements Pie Chart innovation, crit-

ical approaches involve establishing transparent goals, engaging stakeholders, and managing risks, complemented by efficient resource allocation, collaborative development, and educator training. Continuous quality assurance, documentation, and evaluation processes bolster the long-term viability and advancement of the pie chart integration, facilitating profound exploration of art elements in educational environments.

Stakeholders in the Art Elements Pie Chart procedure of implementation give contributions for goals, objectives, and curriculum alignment in addition to supporting the allocation of resources and teacher preparation. Their participation promotes collaboration, guarantees adherence to project goals, and amplifies the pie chart's efficacy when incorporated into learning environments. By fulfilling their respective roles and responsibilities, these stakeholders collaborate to ensure the effective integration of the Art Elements Pie Chart into the educational setting, enhancing students' understanding and appreciation of art elements.

Curriculum Developers: Curriculum developers are responsible for aligning the pie chart implementation with educational standards and objectives. They design instructional materials and provide guidance on integrating the chart into existing curriculum frameworks.

School Head: The school head oversees the implementation process, ensuring that resources are allocated appropriately and supporting educators in integrating the pie chart into teaching practices. They provide leadership and facilitate communication among stakeholders.

Parents and Guardians: Parents and guardians play a supportive role by encouraging students to engage with the pie chart at home and participating in discussions about its benefits. They may also advocate for its use in parent-teacher meetings and school events.

Students: Students actively engage with the pie chart during classroom activities, discussions, and assignments. They explore art elements using the chart as a guide and provide feedback on its effectiveness in enhancing their understanding of artistic concepts.

Other Stakeholders: Other stakeholders, such as community members, local artists, and educational organizations, may provide additional resources, expertise, or advocacy to support the successful implementation of the pie chart. They contribute to creating a rich learning environment and promoting appreciation for the arts within the community.

c. Timeline

During the pre-implementation phase of the Art Elements Pie Chart, which commences at the onset of the school year, teachers allocate two one-hour sessions for preparation. In the initial session, instructors introduce the chart's functionalities and demonstrate its usage, emphasizing its benefits and addressing any inquiries or apprehensions from students. Subsequently, in the second session, teachers engage in hands-on practice with the Art Elements Pie Chart to analyze artworks. This practical exercise fosters educators' confidence in utilizing the tool effectively within their teaching methodologies, establishing a robust groundwork for its integration throughout the academic year.

During the implementation phase of the Art Elements

Pie Chart, which follows the pre-implementation phase conducted at the beginning of the school year, teachers transition from preparation to active utilization of the chart in their teaching practices. They integrate the Art Elements Pie Chart into their lesson plans and classroom activities, incorporating it as a visual aid for analyzing artworks and teaching art concepts. Throughout the academic year, educators continually refine their use of the chart based on student feedback and their own experiences, ensuring its seamless integration into the curriculum, and enhancing students' understanding and appreciation of art elements. The Art Elements Pie Chart will be integrated into the standard curriculum for any lesson that involves analyzing elements of art, irrespective of the artwork under study. Through its consistent incorporation throughout the academic year, students will have the opportunity to continuously develop and reinforce their skills in understanding the elements of art.

In the post-implementation phase, the Element of Art Pie Chart was presented during LAC Sessions as an exemplar of innovative teaching resources for educators. Moreover, Action Research was conducted to evaluate its effectiveness and gather data to validate its efficacy. Based on this assessment, adjustments may be considered for the innovation, including modifications to materials, revisions to implementation strategies, or enhancements to support mechanisms. Additionally, opportunities for potential expansion of the innovation may emerge to cater to more students or address additional learning requirements, potentially involving its adaptation to diverse educational settings or subjects. Through continuous evaluation, refinement, and potential expansion, innovation undergoes evolution to better serve the needs of both learners and educators.

d. Resource Utilization

The Art Element Pie Chart requires materials and technology for its creation and operation. This includes chart design materials such as paper or digital canvas, printing materials like ink and paper, as well as technology such as design software, printers, and digital presentation tools, all of which are essential for educators to effectively teach and illustrate various elements of art to students. Efficiently managing resources is essential for developing and implementing the Art Element Pie Chart. This requires careful planning to ensure availability of design materials, printing supplies, and technology. By optimizing resource usage and monitoring inventory, educators can enhance students' understanding of art elements through streamlined chart creation and operation. Teachers can optimize resource utilization and ensure long-term cost-effectiveness and sustainability for the Art Element Pie Chart through strategies like encouraging reuse and recycling of the materials and exploring technology optimization options. Additionally, collaborative resource sharing and providing training sessions on efficient resource management practices empower educators to maximize resource value, minimizing costs and enhancing students' understanding of art elements effectively.

e. Progress Monitoring

Educators/Teachers are responsible for overseeing the day-to-day implementation of the pie chart in classrooms, tracking student engagement, and gathering feedback on its effectiveness. Curriculum Developers ensure the alignment of the pie chart with educational standards, monitor its impact on curriculum goals, and recommend adjustments as needed. School Administrators oversee institutional implementation, provide support, allocate resources, and ensure integration across different levels. Parents/Guardians contribute feedback on their children's experiences, while students provide insights into the chart's usability and impact on their learning.

To track and evaluate the ongoing progress and outcomes of the Elements of Art Pie Chart, educators employ various methods: conduct formative assessments to gauge student engagement and understanding, gather feedback through observations and surveys, and analyze data to identify trends and areas for improvement. Through continuous refinement and stakeholder engagement, educators ensure the chart remains effective in enhancing student learning experiences.

The teacher employs assessment and observation record sheets to track progress of the students in facilitating informed decision-making. Also, checking the least learned competencies to see if there would be progress in terms of analyzing elements of art competency of the students and checking its effectiveness.

refinement will also improve teaching effectiveness, align with curriculum goals, and ensure long-term sustainability in art education.

V. SUSTAINABILITY PLAN

To sustain the implementation of the element of art pie chart in the future, several specific steps are planned: Continued Professional Development: Offer ongoing training and support for educators to ensure they remain proficient in utilizing the pie chart effectively in their teaching practices. Regular Evaluation and Feedback: Establish mechanisms for continuous evaluation and feedback from educators, students, and stakeholders to identify areas for improvement and inform future enhancements to the implementation process.

These sustainability actions mitigate potential challenges post-implementation of the element of art pie chart by enhancing educator proficiency through ongoing professional development, addressing risks associated with insufficient training or knowledge gaps, and facilitating continuous improvement through regular evaluation and feedback mechanisms, enabling timely adjustments to address evolving needs and mitigate risks before escalation.

The enhancement plans for the Element of Art Pie Chart include continuous evaluation to gather feedback and refine its layout and functionality based on user input. Strategies also involve integrating technology, providing professional development, allowing customization, making data-driven decisions, and fostering stakeholder engagement for continuous improvement. Engaging with educational experts and researchers offers valuable perspectives on pioneering teaching methods and instructional approaches, fostering ongoing improvement of the Elements of Art Pie Chart.

As the Element of Art Pie Chart is refined and implemented, it is expected to lead to enhanced student understanding and increased engagement with art elements. This

Output/Outcome	Beneficiaries
Improved academic performance	Students
Help in teaching and learning process	Teacher and students
Enhanced strategies	Teacher
Improved the least learned competency under analyzing the art elements	Teacher, Student and Administrator

Fig. 3: Innovation Output/Outcome

REFERENCES

- Addison, N., Burgess, L., Steers, J., & Trowell, J. (2018). *Understanding art education: Engaging reflexively with practice* [Retrieved on February 28, 2024]. Routledge. <https://www.routledge.com/Understanding-Art-Education-Engaging-Reflexively-with-Practice/Addison-Burgess-Steers-Trowell/p/book/9780415367400>